

IGSN 2040 Technical Model

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Introduction

This document is based on the outcomes of the workshop of the IGSN 2040 Technical Steering Committee held in Canberra in May 2019 (see Klump et al. 2020) and the discussions held at the workshop of the IGSN Organisational Steering Committee in Tacoma, WA, in July 2019. At the technical workshop we started out from the architectural design principles that should guide the development of the IGSN system architecture. In the next step, we went through three common IGSN use scenarios and identified the personas¹ involved in each step. Having identified the elements of some of the core processes, we defined which elements were essential to the functioning of the IGSN system (Minimum Viable Product, MVP).

The outcomes of the technical workshop in May 2019 were discussed at the organisational workshop in July 2019. The organisational workshop analysed the value proposition of IGSN and the requirements that have to be met to implement the value proposition.

The definition of an MVP does not mean that IGSN should not offer any services beyond the MVP. Instead, the MVP should be seen as a starting point with further services added in the future as additional resources become available.

In this document, we also want to make a clear distinction between different roles in the IGSN system to define which functions should be core functions of the IGSN Organisation (IGSN e.V.), of the IGSN Agents, and which functions are performed by the IGSN user community. For IGSN e.V. this means that some functions are essential to its purpose, while other functions can be added in the future, possibly as revenue-generating services.

User story: Finding information about samples for reuse

Consider the (hypothetical) process for a researcher trying to discover information about useful samples for their next paper:

1. Alice has been talking to Bob recently at the latest conference for their research community about some cool work he's been doing on plant growth using synchrotron imaging. They decide that they need to collaborate on collecting some more data for their next research paper relating plant elemental abundances to environmental effects.
2. Alice wonders whether there are others in their research community who have already published useful environmental data - rather than go to the effort of collecting new data she might be able to reuse existing work! A search throws up a couple of

¹ A persona, in user-centered design, is a fictional character created to represent a user type that might use a site or product in a similar way. (Lidwell et al., 2010)

Google Dataset links, and a link to several collections in GBIF's portal which look interesting.

3. Heading to the GBIF portal, Alice is able to refine her search by specifying the types of observations she wants to collect. She notices that several datasets have something that looks like a DOI URL - putting these in her browser she is taken to the landing page to see other data which have been collected on these samples.
4. Alice uses the portal to aggregate the samples she is interested in (those taken from areas with environmental monitoring data) and shares these with Bob. Together they realise that another institution (CSIRO) has some closely related samples which they would like to analyse and add to their dataset.
5. Alice and Bob call Charlotte, the lab manager at CSIRO and ask whether they can use the samples for their project. Since they aren't going to destructively measure anything Charlotte is happy to share, provided Alice shares the data she obtains.
6. Charlotte packages and send the samples to Alice's institution. She also updates the sample metadata to reflect the fact that Alice's institution is now responsible for these samples and is also allowed to update new observational data on these samples.
7. Alice and Bob take the samples to the Synchrotron for imaging and end up with a ton of data that they make available via Datacite and the local data services. They update the sample record with links to these new data resources and information about the methods they used (including identifiers for the synchrotron beamline and instrument metadata).
8. Bob packages up the samples and sends them back to Charlotte. Charlotte sees that Alice and Bob have made their data available and updates the sample record to note that CSIRO once again has control of the sample and identifier links.
9. Alice and Bob write an award-winning paper in a top tier journal covering their findings. They use the Datacite and IGSN references for the samples to acknowledge the crucial role that both the other researchers in their community, as well as Charlotte and CSIRO, and the Synchrotron played in enabling their science. Since the journal understands how to track all these identifiers, they are able to credit all the institutions involved for their support in advancing human knowledge.

What can we learn from this story? Regardless of your research experience there will be much that is familiar to you - we rarely start research *ab initio* and usually rely on other work, other institutions, other samples and other approaches to answer our research questions. Acknowledging these supports is the right thing to do and makes it easier for supporting functions to be supported themselves by showing all the science they enable.

This story is also a FAIR² utopia. The reality today is that this story would be mostly about painful interactions! There are many roadblocks in the way of data and sample reuse of the form that we've just described. Alice might have only been able to find data for existing samples in three different locations and need to contact the authors to verify that the data refers to the same samples. Alice or Bob would probably have to know that CSIRO held those samples, and even if they did they would need to know that Charlotte is responsible

² Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Packer, A. L., Gray, A. J. G., Mons, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

for them. If they got hold of the samples then they might forget to return them later. Or the data they collect might be available through Datacite but CSIRO might not get that link back to update their records.

The problem: creating a loosely coupled web of samples and data

IGSN's future architecture is fundamentally about making collaboration and management of samples and data about samples easier to enable cool new research. However it's not immediately clear from this story where IGSN's role comes into play (except that we provide an identifier for the samples). Let's try and generalise the players in this story to draw out the role of IGSN. We will do this using personas. A persona is a fictional character created to represent a user type that might use a site or product in a similar way and is a useful way of describing the context for an actor in the system: i.e. their requirements and their motivation for using IGSN.

Returning to the story, we see several key personas emerge. We'll start with the front-end users - the researchers Alice and Bob:

- A **researcher** who just wants to find useful samples and information about those samples. The driving motivation for this persona is to *do great science, and get credit for it* as easily as possible. Secondary motivations include making it easier to manage their own sample data, and develop collaboration opportunities.
- We assume that researchers are grouped in a **research community**³ (which may be formal or informal). Research communities are connected by common sample types, common observations and common use-cases for samples. The driving motivation for the community is *to improve collaboration and scale research efforts*. Different research communities may have widely varying metadata requirements (e.g. geo-* communities require spatial information, while for materials science or biological communities this might be optional).

The research community is a crucial component of the proposed IGSN architecture. Although the research community is latent in the story above it is crucial for Alice and Bob in developing their collaboration (through a common language, shared problems, and common spaces to collaborate/meet up, e.g. at conferences).

Many research communities already exist at a range of scales from informal groupings of researchers who connect at conferences, to institutional communities like CSIRO or universities, to formal cross-organisational groups (e.g. GGIC, IODP, ICDP), to federated communities (e.g. Pangaea, DataCite, DISSCo etc). It's also important to note that for historical reasons a lot of IGSN eV's current persona lies in their role as a research community - for geological samples.

³ Designated User Community: An identified group of potential Consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the Archive and this definition may change over time. (CCSDS, 2012 page 1–11)

The aim of IGSN eV should be to enable these communities to own and manage their samples and data as simply as possible and describe samples and data with attributes that matter the most for their use cases.

To connect communities and make sample data FAIR we require:

- **Community data aggregators** - many research communities already have aggregators which are adapted to the context of that community (e.g. GBIF, survey portals, Google Dataset Service etc). The driving motivation for a data aggregator should be to *provide a good user experience for researchers* in their community - aggregators who do not do this will not get used and eventually die. Good user experience includes making data available in forms that can be easily consumed by their community, and making services reliable and performant. Researchers will generally gravitate towards using a search portal adapted and trusted in their community rather than a more general portal (especially given more general often means worse UX).
- **Community IGSN publishers** who provide IGSN minting services and minimal links to data and metadata associated with the IGSNs they have minted. Publishers govern an IGSN namespace and may federate to other publishers. Publishers have requirements around providing the 'persistent and unique' parts of the IGSN PID system. Publishers will often also have sample management requirements in that they are the repository for physical specimens and generally will have their own support requirements for managing these (e.g. institutional LIMS)

In the story above there are examples of aggregators (Google, GBIF) who provide progressively more detailed search and discovery, and publishers (other researchers via Datacite, CSIRO via some unspecified mechanism to GBIF) who provide access to samples and data about samples.

Both of these personas are currently carried out by allocating agents in the current system but this leads to tension between the drive to better serve the community through better services vs longer-term sustainability concerns (i.e. new services mean more ongoing support costs). The key shift in the new architectural proposal is to separate these concerns.

By separating these personas we can clarify the requirements for both aggregators and publishers. We propose that a publisher doesn't have to make the data *useful or performant*, just *available eventually*. This distinction means that any user (e.g. a researcher or aggregator) wanting to use information directly from an allocating agent needs to be *fault tolerant* and not time limited. The other side to this tradeoff is that allocating agents can use relatively cheap hosting and their own tools to provide information to the network (e.g. as simple as read-only documents on a public cloud provider through to a hand-rolled server implementation), allowing them to massively reduce their costs.

Note that this story shows that there isn't just 'one portal to rule them all', or one tech-mediated access experience that gets the job done (e.g. Alice and Bob still call Charlotte to discuss access to the samples). Rather there is a network of publishers and

aggregators which provide a toolbox of tools to support Alice and Bob in their quest for new knowledge.

How do publishers and aggregators know about each other? To make these systems work we also require some central coordination:

- A **central registry/technical persona** who (a) connects the identifiers to the Handle System and (b) provides the central clearing point linking agents with other players who want to use the datas and samples.
- A **central governance persona** who mediates between agents and aggregators and provides a space for decision making about how communication should occur (protocols and schemas), and also acting as a link to broader data and web bodies (e.g. Handle, OGC, W3C, IANA, ...).

Both of these roles are currently carried out by IGSN e.V. and we would see these continue in the new architecture.

Changes moving from current state to future state

Currently IGSN is an excellent combination of lean centralised functions that are supported by federated services. This has given IGSN the ability to adapt to requirements arising from new communities joining the system. To accommodate a more diverse community of users and larger number of sample registrations requires a number of changes.

For IGSN:

- Separation of the 'geological community' part of IGSN from the core delivery of IGSN e.V. The geological community part needs to be sustained and grown, but it is no longer the only game in town for IGSN to support.
- Development of new research communities under the IGSN umbrella. Support to develop new communities, data schemas, processes (e.g. via third party like ESIP).
- Processes for determining how IGSN e.V. will relate to existing community players (e.g. GBIF) or top-level country agents (e.g. AU naming via GA vs AUQL for Qld survey).
- Development of new aggregation services - ideally a business case for each of these. These can be very small/experimental. Reducing the barrier to experimentation allows us to adopt an MVP/fail-fast strategy and don't be afraid to cull a service if there is no justification for it.

For current allocating agents:

- Separation of the publishing persona from the aggregator persona - making a choice as to what roles they want to take on.
- Support to move to a new architecture, including determining whether they want to take on an aggregation role or remain a publisher.

For aggregators (new role):

- Understanding their part in the IGSN universe - how should they get involved? Is there any motivation to get involved?

Other questions

1. Why shouldn't IGSN e.V. take all the aggregation? Why shouldn't agents do it?
2. What is the role for IGSN? Key principle here is that we should not be trying to achieve sustainability for IGSN e.V. by growth (since that will crowd out community) - staying small and focused means you need less resources to be sustainable!
3. What is needed? Explicit architecture of the roles in this network, and agreements on performance and communication (and also a transition plan from the existing IGSN architecture to the proposed new architecture)

Analysis of Elements and Workflows

IGSN Design Manifesto⁴

- Our domains deserve research-specific software.
- Diverse practices and limited resources require generalised software.
- Do one thing well with modular and federated software (but slice the pie thoughtfully).
- Open-source software supports open research and has other advantages (but is difficult to maintain).
- Scope requirements carefully.
- Invest in outreach and engagement.

Architectural Design Principles

We started by outlining the design principles for the future IGSN system architecture.

- Data is becoming more mobile
- IGSN as part of the Research Graph
 - Persistence of samples and related metadata
- Connect physical samples to digital context, provide context
 - Commodity platform
 - Usability in field and lab
 - Findability

⁴ From: Ross, S., Ballsun-Stanton, B., Cassidy, S., Cook, P., Sobotkova, A., & Klump, J. (2020). FAIMS 3.0: Electronic Field Notebooks. In CAAA Digital Archaeology Conference 2020.

- Schema generator
- Usability in the field and lab applications, supporting user communities – users and best practices
- Readability of the identifier
- Cope with bulk registration
- Offline maintaining before registration
- SLAs IGSN – Agent – Client
- Reference to community schemas
- Simple and Stable Registration API

Roles and Example Workflows

As the next step, we identified the personas in the IGSN ecosystem. We then outlined three example workflows and identified the personas involved in these workflows. The example workflows were:

- From sample to publication
- Obtaining a sample for reuse
- A community of practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991) identifies the need for a new sample description

The workflows area idealised, not all components necessarily exist at this point in time.

Personas involved in IGSN processes:

- A. Sample Provider (individual) is the originator or producer of a sample
- B. Sample Information User requires information about a sample
- C. Sample Information Aggregator as a Consumer harvests sample catalogues and compiles these into value-add information products such as portals, meta-catalogues.
- D. Collection Manager is the curator of a collection of samples
- E. Sample Information Aggregator as a Provider
- F. Schema Developers define description metadata schemas for samples
- G. Communities of Practice is a group of people who are active practitioners and who share a field of work as a common ground.
- H. IGSN Agent
- I. IGSN Registrar (IGSN e.V.)
- J. International Standards Bodies (e.g. RDA)
- K. pro
- L. Manuscript Author
- M. Application Developers
- N. Lab Managers
- O. Data Repository

Example Workflow: Sample to Publication

1. A collects sample
2. A registers sample with D, H, N

3. A, N makes observations on sample, derives samples (optional loop-back to 1)
4. B, C perform data analysis and use external data
5. L writes paper and submits manuscript containing IGSN to K
6. A, D, N, O deposit data
7. B, I, K verify identity of samples and data

Example Workflow: Obtain Sample for Reuse

1. B has search criteria for samples
2. M enables search
3. B evaluates search results
4. B selects samples
5. B evaluates data provided by O
6. B selects samples for reuse
7. B requests sample from D
8. B, D1, D2, H1, H2 update custodian
9. Link to “sample to publication” workflow
10. H update sample information at I

Example Workflow: Community of Practice Requires Development of a Sample Description Standard

1. A, B identify the need for a new sample description standard
2. G recognises the need for a new sample description standard
3. F, G, H develop a draft
4. F, G, H, I, J, K go into a black hole
5. I adopts draft
6. C, H, M, O build reference implementation and cool gadgets
7. A collects metadata in new description schema

Services and Minimum Viable Product

Following on from the workflows and involved personas, we extracted the services needed to support the workflows and then mapped these services to personas that use or provide these services.

Table 1: Services and Minimum Viable Product

I is the IGSN Registrar (IGSN e.V.). H is an IGSN Agent. C is an Information Aggregator offering value-added services (e.g. search portal)

Service	Sample to Publication	Obtain Sample for Reuse	MVP IGSN Registry	MVP IGSN Agent
Sample Doc App	A, (M, N, D)			
Sample Metadata upload	A, H, D, L			required

Sample Registration	A, H, I		needs update	required
Sample Discovery Service	A, B, C, N, O	B, M, C		
IGSN Resolver	I		available	
Data Submission	A, L, O			
IGSN Validator	K, I, B			
Federated Data Search		B, H, M, O		
Sitemap Registry		H, I, M	missing	publish to registry
Schema Registry		H, I, M		required
Sample Request		B, D, F		
IGSN Ownership Transfer		D, H, I		
Authentication Service		H, I	needs update	
Namespace Allocation		H, I	needs update	

In the last step, we identified the services required for a minimum viable product (MVP) for the IGSN central registry and for an IGSN in a Box services deployment for an IGSN Agent.

IGSN 2040 System Architecture

Figure: Schematic diagram of the IGSN system architecture and user interactions.

Figure: Overview of IGSN elements

Solid boxes: Minimum viable product; Outlined boxes: Elements adding to the minimum viable product.

IGSN Registry

Minting Service

The IGSN Minting Service receives requests to register IGSN from IGSN Agents and mint Handles pointing to the URL nominated by the IGSN Agent. The Minting Service checks whether the IGSN is well formed and whether the IGSN Agent is authorised to mint an IGSN in the respective namespace, pointing to the nominated base URL.

The IGSN Minting Service receives requests from IGSN Agents to update IGSN registrations. The minting service checks whether the IGSN Agent is authorised to make changes to the respective IGSN registration.

The IGSN Minting Service records the transactions initiated by the IGSN Agents for accounting and billing of service charges (given this is part of the business model).

IGSN Resolver

The IGSN Resolver is available on the net to resolve IGSNs using the form <https://igsn.org/{igsn}> and direct them to the URL of the registered resource. In addition, the

function of the IGSN resolver can be offloaded onto the Handle system, as any Handle server is able to resolve an IGSN URL.

Sitemap Registry

The Sitemap Registry is a registry of sitemaps contributed by IGSN Agents. It can be used by Information Aggregators to instruct their web crawlers which pages to index for domain or application specific services.

Schema Registry

The Schema Registry is a registry of metadata schemas endorsed by communities of practice for use on their landing pages.

Vocabulary Registry

The Vocabulary Registry is a registry of metadata vocabularies endorsed by communities of practice for use on their landing pages.

Validation Service

The IGSN Validation Service the following services:

- validate that an IGSN exists
- check whether a sample has already been registered to avoid duplicate registrations
- Check whether the web endpoint defined by an IGSN exists
- Future extension of the service could perform automated quality checks on the structure and content of the web endpoints defined by an IGSN.

Administrative Services

- Authentication and authorisation
- Accounting and billing
- Name space requests
- Transfer of custodianship

IGSN Agent

Minting Service

The Minting Service is offered by IGSN Agents to IGSN Users who want to obtain or register and IGSN.

Landing Pages

Landing Pages are the web endpoints to which an IGSN handle is resolved. They contain a description of the referenced object (physical specimen, aggregation, sampling feature). The description must conform to the minimum standards laid down by the Community of Practice

which is to consume the contents of the Landing Pages. This includes serving the metadata in an agreed JSON format.

Sitemap

Sitemaps are an easy way for webmasters to inform search engines about pages on their sites that are available for crawling. Sitemaps allow crawlers to pick up all URLs in the Sitemap and learn about those URLs using the associated metadata. In the context of IGSN Agents, Sitemaps are used to direct crawlers from Information Aggregators to the web endpoints that are relevant to their service.

Note: The details describing the Information Aggregator and IGSN User were elaborated in the peer-reviewed manuscript on the IGSN Future Architecture.

Division of functions between the IGSN Organisation and the IGSN user community

Table: Overview of IGSN functions grouped by functions central to the IGSN organisation and its Agents, and functions of the IGSN community.

	Technical Bucket: IGSN e.V. and IGSN Agents	Community Bucket: Information Aggregators and IGSN users
Motivation / Role	IGSN 'must'/provides Should be as cheap as possible Should be as minimal as possible Should scale to entire network (global reach, billions of samples)	IGSN 'may'/enables May only be relevant to some communities Sharing should be encouraged!
Services	Resolution Registration (API, Schema) Basic discovery of agents	Making data relevant to end-users via services (e.g. WFS for spatial samples, CSV, mapping tools, etc) Value-add to data e.g. extracted knowledge graph, machine learning services
Schemas	Schema hosting (schema.igsn.org) Authoritative schemas for various types (XML, JSON) –	Community schema development

	IGSN PID kernel	
Vocabularies	IGSN registration metadata (as minimal as possible) Authoritative sources? Are we 'bless' a particular community as authoritative? Vocab hosting for core vocab Provide a process for getting vocab accepted once the community decides what this is	Vocab hosting for descriptive vocab

An initial list of 22 high level points was created during the session, it was then separated into two groups - **requirements** and **values**. The items on the lists were then evaluated for the following conditions - if it '**exists and is done well**', if it '**exists but may not be adequate for the future**', and if it is an '**important need not yet met**'. The original lists created during the meeting can be found in the day two summary.

Following the workshop, the Project Steering Committee extracted key points raised during the workshop that aligned with these **requirements** and **values**. The results were then re-assessed and the list of requirements was reorganized around emerging themes.

Table one below lists the 7 themes and the individual **requirements** points identified during the workshop. Table two contains the list of **values**. Each table is followed by the associated key points extracted from the workshop discussions.

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